

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12515680>

MECHANISMS OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS

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Abstract: *This article presents the mechanisms of students' creative activity and the concepts of creativity, creative activity and activity.*

Key words: *creativity, creativity, imagination, fantasy, sensitivity, communicative-organizational.*

Creativity means "reshaping" - creating a new form using the elements of an existing form. "Reformation" creativity involves the discovery of a new form that resembles a previously known form. Creativity is "transferring from one form to another" - in this process, a new pattern of rules, a drawing, a new type of certain structures emerges. Newly created forms are not new interpretations of old forms. As soon as the rules are created, the creative person begins to create new rules based on them. After that, it is a puzzle to open up forms of activity, to discover forms that have never been used before. Commenting on the development of the creativity of a future specialist, it is worth saying that the conclusions given by M.G.Yarashevskiy in this regard are noteworthy. A systematic approach to the creative process requires the study of three-dimensional content and their interrelationship. They consist of objects and events, social and personal content:

1) the composition of things and events is a heuristic, a mental "fabric" that creates a new image of a thing, then it turns into a scientific text and emerges as new ideas, theories and discoveries. These heuristics consist of: analogies, metaphors, comparisons, models, and usually form the content of thinking and have a visual form.

2) social content - according to M. G. Yarashevsky, such creativity is visible as a cognitive-dialogical "initial activity". Therefore, opponents and alternatives also give impetus to the development of creative processes.

3) personal content - it consists of personal aspiration, internal purposeful desire and private qualities of the subject of creativity, and consists of new signs and changes that appear in the continuous organization of creative processes.

Creativity is a form of human activity that performs a variable function. Especially the personality of his students, L.S. Vygotsky emphasizes the role of creativity as follows: "Keep in mind that creative abilities serve as a normal and permanent satellite in human development."

In his dictionary, S.M. Vishnyakov explained that creativity, creative activity is a qualitatively new, socially and historically unique activity. From the point of view of some scientists, creativity is the creation of new information in a certain field of science, technology, production, art or people's life in general.

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Creativity is a combination and transformation of existing knowledge

Imagination is the ability to create new emotional or mental images in the imagination

Fantasy is the imagination or creation of results in situations that are not required or are not sufficient the condition of expressed creative activity

Sensibility is the ability of a person to understand

Mechanisms of student's creative activity Mechanisms of student's creative activity

Creativity is a type of activity characteristic of a person, which is manifested in the process of direct interest, pleasure, striving for a new result. Also, this process includes the process from the emergence of creativity in the human mind to its transformation into a material and spiritual product. A person's need for creative activity indicates a desire for new, previously untargeted creativity in activity.

Creativity is a process of activity, the result of which is the creation of qualitatively new objects and spiritual values, or the result of objective renewal. The

main criterion that distinguishes the creativity of production (that is, the product) is the originality of its results. In creativity, not only the result is valuable, but also it itself.

Creative activity is a form of human or collective activity, which did not exist before, but is understood by quality as a new approach.

Imagination - the ability to see new images by processing mental components is the ultimate experience. In addition, imagination is a mental process that organizes the creation of new images (presentations) by processing information from previous experiences and ideas. Yu.N. Kulyutkin, one of our scientists, considers this phenomenon "ability". G. Sele believes that imagination is a very important mental process for the development of creativity and creative thinking. The creator talks about imagination as one of the characteristics of a person. In his opinion, it is bran to combine imagination with the ability to think.

The concept of creative activity is also a very complex and ambiguous concept. Creative activity in the objective sense is the creation of things that do not yet exist, on the basis of existing things. At the same time, creativity is expressed not only by novelty, but also by its social value as benchmarks.

Imagination is a person's ability to create spontaneous or deliberate situations, it is the ability of a person to form images, representations, ideas and leadership, important in mental processes such as modeling, planning, creativity, play, memory, thinking plays a role, moreover, fantasy is a person or group of people expressing their desires, but not the corresponding reality. Also, this situation can be called impovization. Fantasy means writing. This ability is a condition of human creative performance. Fantasy manifests itself in the creation of a work activity or model, when a visual "picture" is not required. For example, a writer can make solid work based on fragmentary archival sources, supplementing them with their own essays. Fantasy techniques include emphasis, simile, and writing.

Intuition or feelings are stable emotional experiences of a person that arise in relationships with the outside world. Emotions are formed and produced during human development and education. In addition, it is explained in the dictionaries that intuition or feeling is a reflection in the brain of certain properties of things and events in the world. Intuition is the first stage and component of knowing the world. On the basis of sensations, forms of emotional cognition, such as perception, arise. Sensation appears in physical, physiological, psychological processes. In the physical process, any objects and events affect the sensory organs and stimulate the peripheral ends of the corresponding sensory nerve.

According to T. N. Kovalchuk, creativity is a process of human activity that creates qualitatively new information and spiritual values.

In the dictionary of a practicing psychologist developed by S. Golovin, creativity is interpreted as a mental process of developing new valuable ideas, creating new material and spiritual benefits.

Creativity is the creative ability of a person - the ability to come up with unusual ideas, deviate from the framework of traditional thinking, and quickly solve problematic issues. It is characterized by constant readiness to create new ideas and is considered a component of the ability structure.

In the National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, the concept of creativity is the work of a creator, activity specific to a creator; a short definition is given in the form of a completionist.

Pedagogy encyclopedia says "Creative activity is a form of human or collective activity to create something qualitatively new. A prerequisite for creative activity is reflected in the flexibility of thought, criticality, integrity of perception. In this dictionary, the concepts of "creativity" and "creativity" are not defined separately.

In the pedagogical-psychological, social-humanitarian and philosophical literature, scientific views and opinions have been put forward regarding the fact that the concept of "creativity" is a non-specific, unique and unique socio-historical type of activity.

Psychologists A.N. Leontev, P.Ya. Gal'perin's scientific research, the consistent implementation of the activity approach, as the goal of teaching in a higher educational institution, envisages training the learner in the performance of a certain activity. The main result of training in these higher educational institutions is the realization of professional tasks, solving operational issues, and forming knowledge. Such a setting of the issue requires a different approach to tools, methods, and the knowledge of the teacher who is training a certain type of activity in the future specialist.

According to the pedagogue scientist V.A. Slastenin, the training of a future specialist involves the education of the knowledge that performs these tasks, i.e. analytical-reflexive, organizational, evaluation-informational, constructive-prognostic, correctional. In our opinion, this point of view of the author largely reflects the ideas about the structure of the teacher's activity. At the same time, the research of the structure of the future specialist's professional competence is a thorough analysis of the pedagogue's work, the level of his training is currently being modernized and the concept of continuous pedagogical education is being implemented by the system of higher and secondary special vocational education. means determining the requirements.

B.Djuraeva's opinion largely corresponds to the implementation of the activity approach: she distinguishes these types of teacher's activity:

Gnostic is the integration of the content of knowledge typical for general and specialized sciences into the structure of typical issues of the specialist's professional activity. Development and classification of educational goals.

- Educational-methodical - choosing the educational-methodical content of general professional and specialized subjects and determining the subject program according to the elements of students' cognitive activities.

- Creative activity - development of educational and methodological support in accordance with the curriculum for all selected topics.

- Communicative-organizational - development and control of communicative-organizational aspects of student-teacher interaction during self-directed work of students.

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